

The Reduction of Ferric Chloride by Citric Acid, Malic Acid and Sugars.

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The reduction of ferric chloride by mandelic acid, lactic acid and tartaric acid was published in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 827). A large amount of work has already been done on the reduction of ferric chloride by organic acids and of ferric salts of organic acids (Benrath, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1919, **74**, 115; Bolin, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, **87**, 490; Allmand and Young, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, p. 3079)

These reactions are characterised by their simplicity. The dark reaction and the temperature coefficient are generally very small and the photochemical reaction is zero molecular. The present paper deals with the reduction of ferric chloride by citric acid, malic acid, glycerine and some sugars, such as glucose, mannose, galactose and levulose.

The source of light was a quartz-mercury burner. The reactions were studied at 435μ and 366μ . These monochromatic radiations were obtained by means of filter Nos. 22870 and 312 of Schott and Gen. The intensity of radiation absorbed was measured as before by means of a Moll thermopile and Moll galvanometer and compared with the intensity of a standard Hefner. Other experimental arrangements were the same as before. Some of the substances, such as citric and malic acids used in these experiments, were all recrystallised but the sugars were used as such without crystallisation. They were preparations of Pfanstiehl Chemical Co. and of high grades of purity.

It was shown in our previous paper that addition of some hydrochloric acid is necessary in order to prevent the disturbing influences due to the hydrolysis of ferric chloride and dissociation of hydrochloric acid produced in course of the reaction. On account of very large absorption in blue and violet region, even a considerable variation in hydrochloric acid concentration did not affect the velocity of reaction appreciably. In the present case, concentration of hydro-

chloric acid has been kept equal to that of ferric chloride. 2 C.c. of the reaction mixture was always titrated with nearly 0.003N thiosulphate solution.

TABLE I.

495 μ m.

FeCl ₃ , 0.03M.	HCl, 0.03M	Citric acid, 0.25M.		Temp., 30°.	
Time in hrs.	0	1.25	2.5	3.75	5
(<i>a-x</i>)	19.2	16.15	13.1	10.1	7.15
<i>x/t</i>		2.44	2.44	2.4	2.36
Glucose, 0.25M.					
Time in hrs.	0	1.25	2.5	3.75	5
(<i>a-x</i>)	19.35	18.25	17.15	16.1	15.05
(<i>x/t</i>)		0.88	0.88	0.84	0.84
Lævulose, 0.25M.					
Time in hrs.	0	1.25	2.5	3.75	
(<i>a-x</i>)	19.2	17.05	16.85	15.85	
<i>x/t</i>		1.0	0.86	0.8	

TABLE II.

Glucose, 0.25M. 366 μ m.

Time in hrs.	0	2	4	6
(<i>a-x</i>)	19.3	18.55	17.8	17.05
<i>x/t</i>		0.375	0.375	0.375

It will be seen that except in the case of lævulose, the reactions are zero-molecular. Galactose also showed a similar fall in the value of *x/t*. In the case of malic acid, mannose and glycerine, truly zero-molecular constants were obtained. The dark reaction was measured in all cases and found to be exceedingly small. Lævulose however showed appreciable dark reaction which is given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Lævulose, 0.25M.	FeCl ₃ , 0.03M.	HCl, 0.03M.	Temp., 30°.
Time in hrs.	0	24	48
(<i>a-x</i>)	19.3	17.75	16.8

TABLE IV.

Influence of Intensity.

	435 μ		366 μ	
	Energy absorbed 1860 ergs. x/t	Energy absorbed 950 ergs. x/t	Energy absorbed 480 ergs. x/t	Energy absorbed 230 ergs. x/t
0.25M-Citric acid	2.43	1.3	0.75	0.38
0.25M-Malic acid	1.3	0.7		
	Energy absorbed 1220 ergs.	Energy absorbed 910 ergs.		
0.25M-Glucose	0.86	0.44	0.375	0.18
0.25M-Galactose	0.88	0.43		

The above table shows that for each frequency of radiation, the reaction velocity is directly proportional to the energy absorbed.

TABLE V.

Influence of Concentration of Ferric Chloride.

Conc. of FeCl ₃ ...	HCl, 0.03M.			Temp. 30°		
	x/t	(435 μ)	x/t	(366 μ)	x/t	(366 μ)
0.25M-Citric acid	2.45	2.43	2.3	0.75	0.74	0.74
0.25M-Malic acid	1.3	1.25	1.25		0.67	0.65
0.25M-Glucose		0.088	0.065	0.38	0.375	0.37
0.25M-Mannose		0.87	0.66		0.35	0.35

It will be seen that the reaction velocity remains practically the same even with fairly wide variation in the concentration of ferric chloride. With glycerine and sugars, however at 435 μ , the value of x/t increased with increase in the concentration of ferric chloride. Intensity measurements showed that the incident 366 μ was completely absorbed in all cases. The incident 435 μ was also completely absorbed by the different mixtures of organic acids and ferric chloride but in the case of mixtures of sugars and ferric chloride with 0.03M-FeCl₃, the absorption was 1220 ergs and with 0.015M-

FeCl_3 solution it was 910 ergs, the values of x/t being 0.87 and 0.65 respectively which are exactly proportional to the energy absorbed. The zero-molecular constants, obtained at $495\mu\mu$ in the case of sugars and glycerine though the incident radiation was not at all completely absorbed, are due to the fact that owing to very small velocity, only 15 to 20 per cent. transformation was measured and within this small change in the concentration of ferric chloride there was no appreciable variation in the energy absorbed.

TABLE VI.

*Quantum Efficiency.*Reaction Cell: 4 cm. $\times$ 4 cm. $\times$ 0.5 cm.

Ferric chloride, 0.03M. HCl, 0.03M. Temp., 30°.

Amount of FeCl_3 , reduced per hr. in c.c. of 0.0032N-thiosulphate solution per 2 c.c. reaction mixture.

	495 $\mu\mu$ Energy absorbed, 1860 ergs.	366 $\mu\mu$ Energy absorbed, 480 ergs.
Citric acid, 0.25M	2.43	0.76
Malic acid, ,,	1.25	0.45
	Energy absorbed 1220 ergs.	
Glucose, 0.25M	0.86	0.37
Mannose, ,,	0.87	0.355
Lævulose, ,,	0.88	0.36
Galactose, ,,	0.87	0.37
Glycerine, ,,	0.63	0.35

Citric acid and ferric chloride at 366 $\mu\mu$.

$$\text{Energy absorbed} = \frac{480 \times 366 \times 10^{-7} \times 16}{6.55 \times 10^{-27} \times 3 \times 10^7} = 1.43 \times 10^{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mols of FeCl}_3 \text{ reduced} &= \frac{0.75 \times 0.0032 \times 6.1 \times 10^{23} \times 8}{2 \times 1000 \times 60 \times 60} \\ &= 1.68 \times 10^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\text{Mols. transformed}}{\text{No. of quanta absorbed}} = \frac{1.68 \times 10^{15}}{1.43 \times 10^{15}} = 1.14.$$

TABLE VII.

Showing the number of mols of FeCl_3 reduced per quantum of energy absorbed with different reductants.

	435 $\mu\mu$	366 $\mu\mu$		435 $\mu\mu$	366 $\mu\mu$
Citric acid	0.8	1.14	Lævulose	0.46	0.55
Malic acid	0.41	0.7	Galactose	0.44	0.55
Glucose	0.43	0.57	Glycerine	0.34	0.53
Mannose	0.44	0.53			

It was shown in our paper already referred to that with mandelic acid as reductant the number of mols of ferric chloride reduced per quantum of energy absorbed was between 1 and 1.8 and with lactic acid and tartaric acid as reductants between 0.45 and 0.8. Hence it may be said that with sugars, glycerine, lactic acid, tartaric acid and malic acid as reductants, about two quanta are necessary per mol of ferric chloride reduced; while with mandelic and citric acids, one molecule of ferric chloride is reduced per quantum of energy absorbed.

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